

THE ROLE OF EDUCATION IN THE CREATIVITY OF ABDULLAH AVLANI

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Annotation: This article discusses the role of education in the work of Abdullah Avlani. Education is the most important stimulus in the works of the writer.

Key words: Enlightener, teacher, publisher, writer of instructive books for children, educator of Uzbek culture, national writer and poet.

One of the most famous representatives of the Uzbek national culture of the late 19th and early 20th centuries is the enlightened poet, playwright, journalist, scientist, statesman and public figure Abdullah Avlani. He was born on July 12, 1878 in the Merganch mahalla of the city of Tashkent in the family of a weaver Miravlon aka. He spent his childhood on the winding streets of the Mirabad mahalla, among the children of railway workers, most of them Russians. He studied at the old Okchi school, then at the madrasah (1885–1886). Engaged in independent reading. He studied Arabic, Persian and Russian. He followed the newspapers and magazines published in Orenburg, Kazan and Tbilisi. In a short time, he became known as an educator and became one of the active representatives of the social and cultural movement in the country.

One of the most important changes in the cultural life of Turkestan at the beginning of the 20th century was the change in school education. During this period, Avloni joined the Jadid movement and became known as one of the active participants in the Jadids in Tashkent. In 1904, Avloni opened a new school in Mirabad and later in Degrezlik (1903–1914), teaching and writing textbooks in a similar manner.

In 1909, the Relief Society was opened at the school, which helped in educational work and taught orphans. He published the first volume of a four-part collection of poems called Literature or National Poems. In partnership with such developers as Munavvarkori, Muhammadjon Podshokhodzhaev, Tavallo, Rustambek Yusufbekov, Nizomiddin Khodjaev, Shokirjon Rakhimi, he founded Nashriyot (1914) and Maktab (1916). He published the newspapers "Tarakkiy", "Shukhrat" (1907), "Osiyo" (1908), "Turon" (1917). In 1918, he became one of the founders and the first editor of Ishtirokiyun, the first newspaper of the

Turkestan Soviet government. During the Soviet period, he held various responsible positions, in whatever position he worked, was engaged in the dissemination of knowledge, education, teaching at universities and colleges. In 1930-34 he headed the department of the Central Asian State University (now Tashkent State University). He died in 1934.

In 1927, Avlani was awarded the title of Hero of Labor. Avlani has been creative for over 30 years. He witnessed the labor events of 1916, which were followed by revolutionary upheavals and the national liberation struggle. In the past, he left, in his words, "dozens of poems and school textbooks, four theater books." Speaking about his place in the history of our culture, it is necessary to single out two aspects: pedagogical activity and literary art. His pedagogical activity, his views on education are important sources in determining the characteristics of education, which rose to a new level at the beginning of the 20th century. The Avlani school was built on the basis of a humanistic and free education, the main task of which was to teach children secular and advanced sciences, to provide young people with the opportunity to participate in the socio-political life of the country. The writer compiled textbooks for these schools.

His "First Teacher" (1911) for former students was reprinted 4 times before the October shift, and "The Last ABC Textbook" - "Second Teacher" (1912) was reprinted 3 times. A special place in the development of socio-pedagogical thought in the early twentieth century. occupies the textbook "Turkish Gulistan or morality" (1913) with moral and didactic content. In it, the issues of education and morality are analyzed for the first time from the point of view of the demands and needs of the twentieth century. Distinguishing traditional good and evil, Avlani takes modernity as the main criterion, substantiating his views with the ideas of Hippocrates, Plato, Aristotle, Saadi Sherazi, Bedil. The writer considered love for the Motherland one of the best human virtues that must be fought for. Motherland is the city and country where everyone was born and raised. Love for language and culture is the love of every person for his people: "The mirror of the life of every people, which shows its existence in the world, is its language and literature. To lose the national language means to lose the spirit of the nation."

Avlani wrote poems, stories and articles under the pseudonyms Hijran, Nabil, Indamas, Shukhrat, Tangrikuli, Surayyo, Shapalak, Chol, Chegaboy, Abdulkhak. It should be noted that Avloni went through a much more difficult life and creative path. He entered literature at a time when the ideological struggle was at an all-time high level. He accepted the struggle for enlightenment

and progress without hesitation. Getting acquainted with the poetry of the poet, you will encounter an interesting situation. There is no romantic poetry in it. He knows social problems, people's grief is more important. He denies all love in the face of the misfortune of the People and Motherland. He "loves his homeland like a friend." He devotes all his love to her. The beginning of the century was a time when Turkestan was very responsible about his fate, the issue of his life and death was being decided. He quickly realized this as an advanced intellectual of the Avlonian period, a great educator, an active supporter of the teachings of the Jadids. His first poetic works were published in the books "Literature or Folk Poems" (I, II, III, Gyuzlar), "Maktab Gulistoni" (1916), "Mardikorlar ashulasi" (1917) and "Sabzavor" tazkirasi (1914). d) and in periodicals. They propagandized knowledge, ignorance, condemned the social and moral foundations of the old system and talked about free and happy time. In this respect, the poems of Avloni of this period are consonant with the poetry of Hamza and Anbar Atin. Avloni made extensive use of finger weights in the literature. He wrote poems to folk melodies and enriched the possibilities of poetry.

One of Avlani's most important contributions to literature was that he was one of the creators of a new literary phenomenon called labor poetry. He wrote poems such as "Words of a Father to a Worker's Son", "Words of a Mother to a Son" and "Forgive" which describe the events of the labor year of 1916. The motherland illuminated the scenes of parting of the laborers who were taken away from the village to the snowy and icy regions of the far north, to black service in the rear, injustice. The melody and style of these poems are very close to the folk songs that played an important role in the national awakening of our people.

Avlani welcomed the February Revolution of 1917 with joy (verses "Kutuldik", "Yotma"). Dedicated to October, he wrote such poems as "March of Freedom" (1919), "In the Ears of the Working People", glorifying the new socialist system. But soon the Russian Soviet regime began to realize that the old tsarist regime was a worse form than before and that Soviet policy was based on hypocrisy. In particular, the refusal to grant the solemnly promised freedom led to the appearance of sad melodies in the poet's work (The Weekly Hour, 1919). Nevertheless, Avloni wrote poems on various topics. Diaries of the "Afghan voyage" about a trip to Afghanistan in 1919-20. are of great importance in studying the history of the establishment of friendly relations between our country and our neighbor.

Avlani was one of the founders of the Uzbek theater. In 1913 he formed the theater group "Turkiston". Turkestan also announced its strict rules. Avloni was both its organizer and ideological and artistic director. The troupe staged the best examples of Uzbek dramaturgy of the early 20th century, such as "Poisonous Life" (Khamza), "The Unfortunate Groom" (A. Kodiriy), "Asli and Karam"). Avloni himself played the roles of Mallu ("Leyli and Majnun"), Faiziboy ("The Unfortunate Groom"), Aliboy ("Wedding"), Boy ("Padarkush").

Avloni "Is it easy to defend the rights?" (1914), the comedies "Pinak" (1915), tragic works such as "We and You", "Portuguese Revolution", "Two Loves", written in 1914-1917, made an important contribution to the development of Uzbek dramaturgy and the popularization of theater . . Through the lawyer Davronbek, he exposed the lawlessness in Turkestan and the ignorance of the world. "Is it easy to be a lawyer?" He created in his work the image of a number of poppies and gamblers, showing that the spiritual life has degraded. He wrote about the struggle against the monarchy, the Portuguese Revolution of 1910, the Young Turk Revolution of 1909 in Turkey ("Two Loves") and expanded the range of topics and ideas in our literature. In "We and You" he described the struggle of Turkestan at the beginning of the 20th century for the old and the new on the example of specific destinies.

The most productive years of Avloni's main creative activity fell on the period before the October Revolution of 1917. Creativity Avloni began to study in the late 60s. Samples of his works in various genres are now published as separate books.

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